

Growth and characterization of Dy_{1-x}Sm_xMnO₃ single crystals by optical floating zone technique

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Abstract:

Dy_{1-x}Sm_xMnO₃ powders were synthesized by solid-state reaction and single crystals were grown using optical floating zone method for the full composition range $0 \leq x \leq 1.0$. Energy dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) confirms the nominal composition for all the grown crystals of Dy_{1-x}Sm_xMnO₃. Rietveld refinement analysis using synchrotron X-ray powder diffraction data on powders obtained after crushing the crystals confirms the orthorhombic phase with *Pnma* space group for all the compositions studied. The lattice parameters and unit cell volume are shown to increase with increasing Sm³⁺ content at the Dy³⁺ site in DyMnO₃. Magnetization measurements on Dy_{1-x}Sm_xMnO₃ single crystals reveal that the Sm³⁺ substitution systematically decreases the rare-earth ordering temperature ($T_{Dy^{3+}}$).

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1. Introduction:

Multiferroic oxides, showing both the magnetic and electric dipolar orderings due to breaking of time and space reversal symmetries below the respective phase transition temperatures, offer the possibility of controlling the electric (magnetic) polarization by applying a magnetic (electric) field [1–4]. These materials have attracted significant interest in the broad field of strongly correlated systems in view of the interesting physics of coupling between magnetic and ferroelectric order parameters and potential technological applications in several multifunctional devices [1,2]. In this context, the family of rare-earth (*RE*) manganites with the general formula $REMnO_3$ ($RE^{3+} = \text{La} - \text{Yb}, \text{Y}$) has received enormous attention in the condensed matter and material physics community due to the richness of phenomena they display such as colossal magnetoresistance, giant magnetocapacitance, spin-driven ferroelectricity, magnetically induced ferroelectricity, multiferroicity, geometrical frustration and rich phase diagram [5–10]. Depending on the growth ambience and the size of RE^{3+} ions, these manganites crystallize either in orthorhombic $Pnma$ space group symmetry or hexagonal $P6_3cm$ space group symmetry [9,11]. In the orthorhombic phase of $REMnO_3$, the Mn^{3+} ion has 6-fold coordination surrounded by oxygen octahedra (MnO_6) while the RE^{3+} ion has 12-fold co-ordination of oxygen [11,12]. On the otherhand, in the hexagonal structure Mn^{3+} ions are located at the *ab* plane forming MnO_5 bipyramidal and this polyhedral is separated along the *c*-axis by a layer of RE^{3+} ions [9,12].

The family of rare-earth manganites, $REMnO_3$ with $RE^{3+} = \text{Tb}, \text{Dy}, \text{Gd}, \text{and Ho}$ has been widely investigated in the past due to the presence of type-II multiferroicity with strong linear magnetoelectric coupling [5,6]. These manganites are paraelectric and paramagnetic at room temperature with an orthorhombically distorted perovskite structure in the $Pnma$ space group [10,11,13–15]. In such manganites, ferroelectricity has been shown to originate from a spiral magnetic structure that breaks both inversion and time reversal symmetry [5]. These rare-

earth manganites are known to show three sequential magnetic phase transitions: paramagnetic to incommensurate sinusoidal antiferromagnetic ordering of Mn spins at $T_1 = 39-44$ K, lock-in transition (also known as incommensurate to commensurate) at $T_2 = 18-27$ K and finally an antiferromagnetic ordering of the rare-earth spins at $T_3 = 6-9$ K [10,11,13–15]. The ferroelectric order emerges at T_2 and gives rise to a peak in the dielectric constant ϵ at this magnetic transition [5,6].

Among the family of $RE\text{MnO}_3$, DyMnO_3 is quite interesting as Dy^{3+} is the largest ion in the rare-earth series for which the orthorhombic phase gets stabilized in air atmosphere and it shows linear magnetoelectric coupling [11,12]. The observed value of ferroelectric polarization ($P \sim 0.2 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$) in DyMnO_3 is nearly three times higher than that for TbMnO_3 [6,7]. It also exhibits a giant magnetocapacitance effect [7]. Exploring the structure-property relationships and tailoring the functional characteristics of manganites may lead to a wide range of applications like magnetic sensors and actuators, magnetic storage media and spintronic devices [1,2,4]. The use of spintronic devices promise, non-volatility, increased processing speed, increased integration densities, easy integration and reduced power consumption over the silicon CMOS technology [3,4].

Towards understanding the intrinsic physical and magnetic properties of the rare-earth manganites, single crystals of different compositions are required. The properties of such rare-earth manganites can be further tailored by cationic substitution at the RE^{3+} site without changing its crystal structure. In this paper, we focus our attention on the orthorhombic phase of DyMnO_3 and its solid solution with SmMnO_3 i.e., $\text{Dy}_{1-x}\text{Sm}_x\text{MnO}_3$. Recently, SmMnO_3 has received revived interest due to its multifunctional properties like magnetocapacitance [16,17], magnetocaloric effect [18], catalytic activity towards oxygen reduction reaction [19] and CO_2 to fuel conversion process [20]. To the best of our knowledge, no information on the single crystal growth of the solid solution series $\text{Dy}_{1-x}\text{Sm}_x\text{MnO}_3$ as well as its properties is available

in the literature except of its end members DyMnO_3 and SmMnO_3 . It is worth to mention that the flux-grown manganite single crystals are usually small and are contaminated with solvent material and also trace amounts of alumina crucible material, both of which are highly undesirable. The present investigation was undertaken to grow large-size single crystals of $\text{Dy}_{1-x}\text{Sm}_x\text{MnO}_3$ in the composition range $0 \leq x \leq 1.0$ using optical float zone method and characterize them for their structure and magnetic properties.

2. Synthesis and characterizations:

The polycrystalline $\text{Dy}_{1-x}\text{Sm}_x\text{MnO}_3$ ($x = 0.00$ to 1.00 with step $\Delta = 0.25$) materials were prepared using a standard solid-state route. Oxides Dy_2O_3 , Sm_2O_3 and Mn_2O_3 of purity $\geq 99.99\%$ were pre-heated at 1023 K for 12 hrs to remove the moisture content before weighing the stoichiometric amounts. The powders were mixed thoroughly using acetone and heated at 1123 K for 24 h in air atmosphere. The heat-treated materials were crushed and again heated at 1523 K for 48 h in air. The phase purity of synthesized powders was examined by powder X-ray diffraction measurements. The synthesized powders were filled into rubber tube, evacuated and then pressed isostatically at a pressure of 70 MPa to get uniform diameter and dense polycrystalline feed rods. The dimension of the feed rods are $7\text{-}9\text{ mm}$ diameter and $60\text{-}80\text{ mm}$ length. The polycrystalline rods were sintered at $1573\text{-}1623\text{ K}$ for 12 h to get the high dense rods. A representative polycrystalline feed rod of $\text{Dy}_{0.50}\text{Sm}_{0.50}\text{MnO}_3$ is shown in Fig. 1(a). Single crystals of $\text{Dy}_{1-x}\text{Sm}_x\text{MnO}_3$ were grown by using four-mirror optical-floating-zone equipment (Model-FZ-T-4000-H-VII-VPOPC, Crystal Systems Corporation, Japan).

The chemical compositions of the grown crystals were checked by energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (Oxford, model no. 51-ADD0048). The crystal orientation and symmetry were checked by Laue diffractometer in the back reflection geometry. High-resolution synchrotron X-ray powder diffraction (SXRDP) data of $\text{Dy}_{1-x}\text{Sm}_x\text{MnO}_3$ were collected at

PETRA III, Germany at energy ~ 60 keV (wavelength $\lambda \sim 0.2070$ Å). The powder samples were filled in a quartz capillary of 0.6 mm diameter and exposed to the incident beam for 60 s. Two-dimensional SXRD pattern was recorded using a Perkin Elmer 1621 detector. LaB6 standard was used to calibrate the sample to detector distance. FIT2D software was used to convert 2D XRD data to 1D pattern [21]. The analysis of the SXRD data was carried out by Rietveld refinement technique using Fullprof suite [22]. Temperature-dependent magnetic measurements were performed using a SQUIDS-based magnetic property measurement system (MPMS, Quantum Design, USA). Temperature-dependent heat capacity (C_p) measurements were carried out on a physical property measurement system (PPMS, Quantum Design, USA).

3. Results and Discussion:

3.1 Optimization of single crystal growth:

DyMnO₃ crystal growth optimization conditions were described in our previous article [11] and a part of this grown crystal is used as a seed for the compositions attempted in this work. The growth of Dy_{1-x}Sm_xMnO₃ crystals were carried out under continuous flowing of air at 2.5 - 4 l/min and the crystal growth rate was varied to 3-6 mm/h. During the growth process upper (feed rod) and lower (seed crystal) shafts were rotated counter clock-wise at speed of 15-25 rpm. During the initial phase of the growth process, it was imperative to fine-tune the halogen lamp power until a stable growth pattern was achieved for various composition. Appropriate lamp power, growth rate, gas flow rate and feed/seed rod rotation, is essential to maintain a stable solid-liquid interface shape near the growing crystal and liquid to solid interface shape near feed material during the entire crystal growth process. These crystal growth parameters were fine-tuned to attain a clear crystallizing interface by closely monitoring the melt through CCD camera. Utilizing the appropriate seed crystal led to the rapid emergence of a large facet and a smooth surface in the growing single crystal. A representative

crystal growth status during seeding, stable growth and growth end recorded by CCD are shown in Fig. 1(b-d)). The smooth growing interface is indicative of the high quality of the growing crystal. The growth parameters were then kept unaltered resulting in the production of a single crystal characterized by a shiny smooth morphology. The same procedure was followed for growing the remaining compositions of $\text{Dy}_{1-x}\text{Sm}_x\text{MnO}_3$. The optimized growth parameters for each composition are presented in Table 1. Fig. 1(e) depicts the representative as grown $\text{Dy}_{0.50}\text{Sm}_{0.50}\text{MnO}_3$ single crystal and corresponding back reflection Laue diffraction pattern is shown in Fig. 1(f). From the number of growth experiments conducted, it is evident that the growth of these crystals was not significantly influenced by the growth rate. Growth rate within the range of 2 to 5 mm/h yielded similar results, matching with the previous literature [6-14]. However, crystal growth was notably sensitive to the atmospheric conditions and the rotation rate. Alternative atmospheres such as pure oxygen or pure argon proved to be unsuitable. For instance, in a pure oxygen environment, the molten zone exhibited bubbles and sudden freezing, making stable crystal growth unattainable. Meanwhile, in a pure argon atmosphere, a mixture of orthorhombic and hexagonal crystal phases emerged.

3.2 Compositional analysis:

The chemical composition of the as-grown single crystals of $\text{Dy}_{1-x}\text{Sm}_x\text{MnO}_3$ were recorded by EDS spectrum and the results are given in Table 2. It is evident from the table that the estimated composition of each element is comparable to the nominal composition.

3.3 Room temperature crystal structure analysis:

The phase purity of the as-grown crystals was verified by analyzing the room-temperature SXRD patterns. The synchrotron XRD patterns of $\text{Dy}_{1-x}\text{Sm}_x\text{MnO}_3$ recorded as a function of Sm composition (x) are shown in Fig. 2. All the peaks in the SXRD patterns of $\text{Dy}_{1-x}\text{Sm}_x\text{MnO}_3$ correspond to the orthorhombic phase with *Pnma* space group. There is no evidence

of any trace of the impurity phase observed in the diffraction patterns. This confirms the single-phase formation of all the grown crystals.

We have also performed the quantitative analysis of the SXRD patterns of $\text{Dy}_{1-x}\text{Sm}_x\text{MnO}_3$ using Rietveld refinement technique [22]. In the refinement, the peak shape and width were modelled using the pseudo-Voigt function while the background can be described by linear-interpolation method. All parameters (scale factor, zero error, background points, width parameters (u, v, w), lattice parameters (a, b, c), thermal parameters and positional coordinates) were varied during the refinement except the occupancy which was fixed to the nominal composition. Fig. 3(a-e) display the observed (filled red circle) and calculated (black continuous line) synchrotron XRD profiles for $\text{Dy}_{1-x}\text{Sm}_x\text{MnO}_3$ using the orthorhombic structure in the *Pnma* space group. It is evident that the observed and calculated profiles show a satisfactory fit for all compositions (x), as can be seen from the flat difference profile given as bottom (blue continuous) line in the same figure. We do not observe any structural phase transition as a result of Sm^{3+} substitution at the Dy^{3+} site, i.e. the crystal structure remains orthorhombic in the *Pnma* space group for all the compositions. The structural parameters obtained after the Rietveld analysis of $\text{Dy}_{1-x}\text{Sm}_x\text{MnO}_3$ are presented in Table 3. The observed unit cell parameters of the end members DyMnO_3 and SmMnO_3 are consistent with the previous reports [13,18,23].

The composition dependence of the lattice parameters and unit cell volume of $\text{Dy}_{1-x}\text{Sm}_x\text{MnO}_3$ is shown in Fig. 4(a, b and c). The unit cell parameter increases linearly with increasing the Sm^{3+} composition and follows the Vegard's law behaviour. This increasing trend of unit cell parameters can be attributed to the fact that the ionic radius of Sm^{3+} (109.8 pm) is larger than that of Dy^{3+} (105.2 pm) [24] and hence substitution of Sm^{3+} at the Dy^{3+} -site would lead to lattice expansion. The bond length and bond angles were also extracted from the refined coordinates. The structure of the orthorhombic DyMnO_3 consists of MnO_6 octahedra and

DyO₁₂ polyhedral units. The shape of the MnO₆ octahedra is distorted due to Jahn-Teller effect of the Mn³⁺ ion. This leads to two types of Mn-O bond lengths. Similarly, the Dy³⁺ ion is coordinated by 12 oxygen atoms with noticeable variations in the Dy-O bond lengths. The composition dependence of some selected bond lengths (Mn-O₁ & Mn-O₂; Dy/Sm-O) and bond angles (O₁-Mn-O₂ and O₁-Dy/Sm-O₂) are shown in Fig. 4(d, e, and f). It is evident that the bond-length and bond angles also increase with increasing the Sm³⁺ composition. Thus, our SXRD confirms the single-phase formation of Dy_{1-x}Sm_xMnO₃ crystals.

3.4 DC magnetization studies on Dy_{1-x}Sm_xMnO₃ single crystals:

The temperature dependence of the dc magnetization of pristine DyMnO₃ crystal under zero-field cooled and field-cooled conditions with field $H = 25$ Oe applied parallel to the c-axis is shown in Fig. 5(a). Evidently, two magnetic transitions $T_N \sim 44$ K and $T_{Dy^{3+}} \sim 8$ K related to the paramagnetic to incommensurately modulated antiferromagnetic structure of Mn³⁺ spins and rare-earth ordering of Dy³⁺ spins, respectively, are clearly seen in the M(T) curve of DyMnO₃. The lock-in transition expected around ~ 18 K is not visible in the M(T) curve possibly due to the high-rising trend of the magnetization below T_N masked this transition. Interestingly, all three transitions have appeared in the specific heat measurements as shown in the inset (i) of Fig. 5(a). We note that the T_N slightly varies between dc M(T) and specific heat measurements. Given the fact that these measurements were conducted using completely different experimental set-ups and each technique has different measurement time scales and heating/cooling rates for the sample. We believe that the differing time scales of the measurement technique may lead to the observed (± 4 K) variation in T_N . Thus our DyMnO₃ crystals exhibit all three transitions consistent with the literature reports [6,10,25,26].

In contrast to DyMnO₃, SmMnO₃ shows a paramagnetic to A-type antiferromagnetic structure of the Mn³⁺ spins at $T_N \sim 55-60$ K [16,18,23,27]. It also exhibits a temperature-induced

magnetization reversal phenomenon characterized by the magnetic compensation temperature at $T_{\text{comp}} \sim 6-9$ K [23,27]. Such spin reversal phenomena were observed in Néel N-type ferrimagnetic compounds like spinel's consisting of two or more magnetic sublattices. In SmMnO_3 , this phenomenon has been attributed to be induced by a Sm^{3+} - Mn^{3+} exchange interaction [27]. More interestingly, the dielectric constant shows an anomaly across the magnetic compensation temperature and gives rise to the magnetodielectric effect [16].

Now, to understand the effect of Sm substitution at Dy-site on the magnetic transitions, we measured the ZFC and FC magnetization on $\text{Dy}_{0.75}\text{Sm}_{0.25}\text{MnO}_3$, $\text{Dy}_{0.50}\text{Sm}_{0.50}\text{MnO}_3$ and $\text{Dy}_{0.25}\text{Sm}_{0.75}\text{MnO}_3$ crystals, as depicted in Fig. 5(b), (c) and (d). It is evident that only one prominent peak corresponding to rare-earth ordering transition at $T_{\text{Dy}^{3+}} \sim 4.8$ K is observed for $\text{Dy}_{0.75}\text{Sm}_{0.25}\text{MnO}_3$ crystal. On the otherhand, for $\text{Dy}_{0.50}\text{Sm}_{0.50}\text{MnO}_3$ crystal, no clear peak corresponding to rare-earth ordering transition was observed within the limit of our $M(T)$ measurements, but it is intended to peak ~ 2 K (see inset of Fig. 5(b) and 5(c)). In the case of $\text{Dy}_{0.25}\text{Sm}_{0.75}\text{MnO}_3$ crystals (see inset of Fig. 5(d)), the transition temperature lies below 2.0 K, exceeding our MPMS system's measurement limit. Additional, milli-kelvin temperature range of magnetic measurements would be required to confirm the rare-earth ordering temperature for 0.75% Sm substitution. The observed magnetic transitions of all Sm-substituted crystals and pristine SmMnO_3 are summarized in Table 4. Here, we note that Sm substitution leads to a significant decrease in the rare-earth ordering temperature. The detailed magnetic analysis of the Sm-substituted crystals is a subject matter of a separate publication.

4. Conclusions:

We have successfully grown large single crystals of the solid solution system $\text{Dy}_{1-x}\text{Sm}_x\text{MnO}_3$ with $x = 0.00, 0.25, 0.50, 0.75$ and 1.0. EDX analysis confirmed the stoichiometry of the grown crystals. Rietveld refinement analysis using synchrotron X-ray powder diffraction

data on powders obtained after crushing the crystals confirm the single-phase formation and orthorhombic structure in the *Pnma* space group for all compositions. The lattice parameters and unit cell volume increase with increasing Sm^{3+} substitution at the Dy^{3+} site as expected due to the larger size of Sm^{3+} . Temperature-dependent dc magnetization and specific heat measurements on pristine DyMnO_3 crystals reveal three magnetic transitions ~ 44 K, 18 K and 8.8 K. Further, the preliminary magnetic study of Sm-substituted single-crystals along the *c*-axis revealed that the rare-earth ordering temperature decreases with increasing Sm-content.

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References:

- [1] W. Eerenstein, N.D. Mathur, J.F. Scott, Multiferroic and magnetoelectric materials, *Nature*. 442 (2006) 759.
- [2] R. Ramesh, N.A. Spaldin, Multiferroics: Progress and prospects in thin films, *Nat. Mater.* 6 (2007) 21.

- [3] N.A. Spaldin, R. Ramesh, Advances in magnetoelectric multiferroics, *Nat. Mater.* 18 (2019) 203.
- [4] X. Xu, C. Binek, Magnetoelectric Multiferroic Materials, *Encyclopedia of Materials: Electronics*, 1 (2023) 633.
- [5] T. Kimura, T. Goto, H. Shintani, K. Ishizaka, T. Arima, Y. Tokura, Magnetic control of ferroelectric polarization, *Nature*. 426 (2003) 55.
- [6] O. Prokhnenko, R. Feyerherm, E. Dudzik, S. Landsgesell, N. Aliouane, L.C. Chapon, D.N. Argyriou, Enhanced ferroelectric polarization by induced Dy spin order in multiferroic DyMnO₃, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 98 (2007) 057206.
- [7] T. Goto, T. Kimura, G. Lawes, A.P. Ramirez, Y. Tokura, Ferroelectricity and giant magnetocapacitance in perovskite rare-earth manganites, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 92 (2004) 257201.
- [8] T. Tajiri, H. Deguchi, M. Mito, A. Kohno, Characteristic Size Effects on the Crystallographic Structure and Magnetic Properties of RMnO₃ (R = Eu, Gd, Tb, Dy) Nanoparticles, *J. Phys. Chem. C*. 125 (2021) 14474.
- [9] P.A. Kumar, A. Kumar, K. Kumar, G.A. Babu, P. Vijayakumar, S. Ganesamoorthy, P. Ramasamy, D. Pandey, Evidence for Spin Glass Transition in Hexagonal DyMnO₃ without Substitutional Disorder, *J. Phys. Chem. C*. 123 (2019) 30499.
- [10] T. Kimura, G. Lawes, T. Goto, Y. Tokura, A.P. Ramirez, Magnetoelectric phase diagrams of orthorhombic RMnO₃ (R=Gd, Tb, and Dy), *Phys. Rev. B*. 71 (2005) 224425.
- [11] P. Aravindh Kumar, A. Kumar, K. Kumar, P. Singh, G. Anandha Babu, P. Vijayakumar, S. Ganesamoorthy, P. Ramasamy, D. Pandey, Growth and characterization of Dy_{1-x}Y_xMnO₃ single crystals by optical floating zone technique: A combined X-ray diffraction and DC magnetization study, *J. Cryst. Growth*. 565 (2021) 126152.
- [12] H. Sim, J. Oh, J. Jeong, M.D. Le, J.G. Park, Hexagonal RMnO₃: A model system for two-dimensional triangular lattice antiferromagnets, *Acta Crystallogr. Sect. B Struct. Sci. Cryst. Eng. Mater.* 72 (2016) 3.
- [13] Y. Chen, H. Yuan, G. Li, G. Tian, S. Feng, Crystal growth and magnetic property of orthorhombic RMnO₃ (R=Sm-Ho) perovskites by mild hydrothermal synthesis, *J.*

- Cryst. Growth. 305 (2007) 242.
- [14] J.L. Ribeiro, Symmetry and magnetically driven ferroelectricity in rare-earth manganites RMnO_3 ($R = \text{Gd, Tb, Dy}$), Phys. Rev. B. 76 (2007) 144417.
- [15] K. Yamauchi, F. Freimuth, S. Blügel, S. Picozzi, Magnetically induced ferroelectricity in orthorhombic manganites: Microscopic origin and chemical trends, Phys. Rev. B. 78 (2008) 014403.
- [16] J.S. Jung, A. Iyama, H. Nakamura, M. Mizumaki, N. Kawamura, Y. Wakabayashi, T. Kimura, Magnetocapacitive effects in the Néel N-type ferrimagnet SmMnO_3 , Phys. Rev. B. 82 (2010) 212403.
- [17] H. Maeda, Y. Ishiguro, T. Honda, J.S. Jung, S. Michimura, T. Inami, T. Kimura, Y. Wakabayashi, Structural investigation of magnetocapacitive SmMnO_3 , J. Ceram. Soc. Japan. 121 (2013) 265.
- [18] C.A. Da Silva, R.S. Silva, E.J.R. Plaza, N.O. Moreno, Magnetic state and magnetocaloric effect of SmMnO_3 , J. Supercond. Nov. Magn. 26 (2013) 2497.
- [19] R.R. Mahalik, I. Hota, S. Soren, A.K. Debnath, K.P. Muthe, P. Parhi, Efficient oxygen reduction reaction of rare earth perovskite SmMnO_3 , Inorg. Chem. Commun. 154 (2023) 110924.
- [20] K. Gao, X. Liu, T. Wang, Z. Zhu, P. Li, H. Zheng, C. Song, Y. Xuan, Y. Li, Y. Ding, Sr-doped SmMnO_3 perovskites for high-performance near-isothermal solar thermochemical CO_2 -to-fuel conversion, Sustain. Energy Fuels. 5 (2021) 4295.
- [21] A. Kumar, P. Singh, R.J. Choudhary, D. Pandey, Effect of Mn-doping on the low temperature magnetic phase transitions of BiFeO_3 , J. Alloys Compd. 825 (2020) 154148.
- [22] J. Rodriguez-Carvajal, Introduction to the Program FULLPROF:Refinement of Crystal and Magnetic Structures from Powder and Single Crystal Data (2001).
- [23] J. Mantilla, M. Morales, W. Venceslau, L. Corredor, P.C. Morais, F.F.H. Aragón, S. William da Silva, J.A. Coaquira, Field-driven spin reorientation in SmMnO_3 polycrystalline powders, J. Alloys Compd. 845 (2020) 156327.
- [24] R.D. Shannon, Revised Effective Ionic Radii and Systematic Studies of Interatomic

- Distances in Halides and Chaleogenides, *Acta Crystallogr. A* 32 (1976) 751.
- [25] R. Feyerherm, E. Dudzik, N. Aliouane, D.N. Argyriou, Commensurate Dy magnetic ordering associated with incommensurate lattice distortion in multiferroic DyMnO₃, *Phys. Rev. B.* 73 (2006) 180401.
- [26] S. Harikrishnan, S. Robler, C. N. Kumar, H. L. Bhat, U. K. Robler, S. Wirth, F. Steglich, and S. Elizabeth, Phase transitions and rare-earth magnetism in hexagonal and orthorhombic DyMnO₃ single crystals, *Journal of Physics: Condensed matter*, 21(9) (2009) 096002.
- [27] J.G. Cheng, J.S. Zhou, J.B. Goodenough, Y.T. Su, Y. Sui, Y. Ren, Exchange field on the rare earth Sm³⁺ in a single crystal perovskite SmMnO₃, *Phys. Rev. B.* 84 (2011) 104415.

Figure 1: (a) depicts the representative prepared polycrystalline feed rod of $\text{Dy}_{0.50}\text{Sm}_{0.50}\text{MnO}_3$. (b-d) display the crystal growth status during seeding, stable growth and growth end recorded by CCD, (e) shows the as-grown $\text{Dy}_{0.50}\text{Sm}_{0.50}\text{MnO}_3$ single crystal and corresponding Laue diffraction pattern is shown in (f).

Figure 2: Left Panel shows the evolution of synchrotron X-ray powder diffraction patterns of $\text{Dy}_{1-x}\text{Sm}_x\text{MnO}_3$ single crystals. The right panel depicts the schematic representation of the crystal structures of orthorhombic $\text{Dy}_{1-x}\text{Sm}_x\text{MnO}_3$ where green, blue and black colour balls indicate the $\text{Dy}^{3+}/\text{Sm}^{3+}$, Mn^{3+} and O^{2-} positions.

Figure 3: Observed (filled red circles) and calculated (black continuous line) profiles of synchrotron XRD data of $\text{Dy}_{1-x}\text{Sm}_x\text{MnO}_3$ ((a) $x = 0.00$, (b) $x = 0.25$, (c) $x = 0.50$, (d) $x = 0.75$, and (e) $x = 1.00$) obtained after the Rietveld refinements using the orthorhombic $Pnma$ space group. The difference profile is shown as blue continuous line in the same figure. The vertical tick marks indicate the expected Bragg peak positions for space group $Pnma$.

Figure 4: Composition dependence of (a) lattice parameters ‘ a ’ and ‘ c ’, (b) lattice parameter ‘ b ’, (c) unit cell volume ‘ V ’, (d) bond lengths Mn-O₁ and Mn-O₂, (e) bond angles O₁-Mn-O₂ and O₁-Dy/Sm-O₂ and (f) bond lengths Dy/Sm-O of Dy_{1-x}Sm_xMnO₃. The error bar in the estimated parameters are smaller than the symbol size.

Figure 5: Panel (a) depicts the temperature dependence of zero-field cooled (ZFC) and field cooled (FC) magnetization of pristine DyMnO₃ with H = 25 Oe parallel to the c-axis. Inset of (a): (i) shows the C_p/T versus T plot for DyMnO₃ and (ii) ZFC M(T) curve on a magnified scale near T_N. Panels (b)-(d) show the ZFC and FC magnetization curves measured at H = 25 Oe for Dy_{0.75}Sm_{0.25}MnO₃, Dy_{0.50}Sm_{0.50}MnO₃ and Dy_{0.25}Sm_{0.75}MnO₃, respectively. Inset of (b)-(d) depict the ZFC M(T) curve on a magnified scale across rare-earth ordering temperature.

Table 1: Optimized growth parameters for Dy_{1-x}Sm_xMnO₃ crystals.

Parameters	DyMnO ₃	Dy _{0.75} Sm _{0.25} MnO ₃	Dy _{0.50} Sm _{0.50} MnO ₃	Dy _{0.25} Sm _{0.75} MnO ₃	SmMnO ₃
Atmosphere air (l/min)	2.75	3	3	3.5	4
Growth rate (mm/h)	5.5	5	4.3	3.7	2.8
Upper Shaft rotation (rpm)	25	25	20	20	15
Lower shaft rotation (rpm)	20	20	17	18	10

Table 2: Results of the chemical composition of o-Dy_{1-x}Sm_xMnO₃ (x = 0.0, 0.25, 0.50 and 0.75) single crystals obtained from the EDX analysis.

Elements	DyMnO ₃				Dy _{0.75} Sm _{0.25} MnO ₃				Dy _{0.50} Sm _{0.50} MnO ₃				Dy _{0.25} Sm _{0.75} MnO ₃			
	Weight %		Atomic %		Weight %		Atomic %		Weight %		Atomic %		Weight %		Atomic %	
	The.	Obs.	The.	Obs.	The.	Obs.	The.	Obs.	The.	Obs.	The.	Obs.	The.	Obs.	The.	Obs.
Dy	74.7	74.1	50	49.2	56.9	58.1	37.5	38.4	38.6	39.5	25	25.8	19.5	21.8	12.5	13.9
Mn	25.3	25.9	50	50.8	25.6	25.6	50	49.8	25.9	25.7	50	49.7	26.4	26.8	50	50.9
Sm	-	-			17.5	16.3	12.5	11.8	35.5	34.8	25	24.5	54.1	51.4	37.5	35.5

Table 3: Refined structural parameters obtained from the Rietveld refinements of Dy_{1-x}Sm_xMnO₃ using *Pnma* space group.

Dy _{1-x} Sm _x MnO ₃	x = 0.00	x = 0.25	x = 0.50	x = 0.75	x = 1.00
a (Å)	5.8494(8)	5.8547(8)	5.8584(6)	5.8646(6)	5.8739(1)
b (Å)	7.3882(2)	7.3936(7)	7.3983(9)	7.4013(4)	7.4077(4)
c (Å)	5.2876(9)	5.2902(3)	5.2945(5)	5.2991(7)	5.3056(2)
V (Å) ³	228.62(14)	229.27(12)	229.90(21)	230.58(17)	230.94(13)
Dy ³⁺ /Sm ³⁺					
x	0.0846(9)	0.1326(4)	0.1187(2)	0.1452(5)	0.1584(9)
y	0.9817(2)	0.9945(1)	0.9901(6)	0.9987(7)	0.9988(4)
z	0.2500	0.2500	0.2500	0.2500	0.2500
Mn ³⁺					
x	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
y	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000
z	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
O ₁ ²⁻					
x	0.4569(7)	0.4678(9)	0.4607(6)	0.4698(7)	0.4789(5)
y	0.1309(6)	0.1394(3)	0.1341(9)	0.1403(4)	0.1496(2)
z	0.2500	0.2500	0.2500	0.2500	0.2500
O ₂ ²⁻					
x	0.1322(7)	0.1368(2)	0.1341(2)	0.1385(7)	0.1472(7)
y	0.2500	0.2500	0.2500	0.2500	0.2500
z	0.5402(8)	0.5449(5)	0.5414(3)	0.5457(1)	0.5528(4)
χ ²	3.6	2.9	2.5	2.7	4.9

Table 4: Summarizes the observed magnetic transitions in o-Dy_{1-x}Sm_xMnO₃ crystals.

Magnetic transitions	DyMnO ₃	Dy _{0.75} Sm _{0.25} MnO ₃	Dy _{0.5} Sm _{0.5} MnO ₃	Dy _{0.25} Sm _{0.75} MnO ₃	SmMnO ₃ Ref. [23,27]
T _{Dy³⁺/Sm³⁺}	8.8 K	4.8 K	~ 2.0 K	< 2.0 K	-
T _{lock-in} / T _{comp}	21.4 K	-	-	-	6-9 K
T _N	43.7 K	-	-	-	55-60 K

Here T_N: Long-range ordered antiferromagnetic transition corresponding to Mn spins, T_{lock-in}: Lock-in transition, T_{comp}: Compensation transition, T_{Dy³⁺/Sm³⁺}: Rare-earth ordering transition.